

THE BASICS OF TEACHING METHODS IN WRESTLING

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Summary This article shows the principles of modern pedagogical training of wrestlers, the activity of the teacher.

The aims and objectives of training: Training in wrestling is the development of a system of skills and experiences that are considered the main unique competition, refereeing, pedagogic, and organizational services of a wrestler and mean a targeted organizational pedagogical process.

The purpose of training is to form a system of knowledge that reflects the concept of the trainer's professional service. This concept includes knowledge and experiences, methods of scientific thinking, educating of creative attitude in conscious and practical actions of the participants.[1]

The general tasks that reflect the specific conditions and features of the study of the theory of wrestling and the method of its teaching are as follows:

- to ensure that the knowledge about the theory of sports and the method of teaching it is optimal, comprehensive and deep enough;
- development of creative abilities;
- formation and improvement of the wrestler's experience of performing general preparatory exercises;
- formation and improvement of methods of fighting techniques, defense and countermeasures;
- formation of optimal size and diversity of technical and tactical actions in competitions;

- formation of skills and experience of training, supervision, conducting competitions and demonstrative competitions;
- formation and improvement of knowledge, experience and skills of discussing techniques of fighting methods;
- acquire the experience of showing and explaining the fighting technique;
- formation and improvement of knowledge, experience and skills of training and improvement of complex technical and tactical actions;
- formation and improvement of experiences of discussing and conducting wrestling lessons;
- forming and improving the skills of refereeing wrestling competitions and organizing mass sports events and conducting them with knowledge and experience.[2]

Teaching principles: In modern pedagogy, teaching principles are explained as basic requirements and guiding rules that determine the difference between the teacher's service and the student's knowledge. Practical pedagogical service is based on the principles of teaching, which serve as a guide for planning, organizing and discussing teaching practice.

The study-training process in wrestling is carried out in accordance with the main principles of physical education: educational uniqueness, comprehensive development, health and practical importance.

The educational uniqueness of teaching means the regulation of the study-training process. Here, with the growth of sports experience of wrestlers, at the same time, personal discipline norms are formed.

Training and educating of the sports reserve is related to the solution of several complex educational issues. In order to achieve high results in sports, training of wrestlers to control, discuss and evaluate technical and tactical actions is of great importance. All this is the result of the educational influence of the trainer, under his guidance, the trainees get the experience of being ready to solve life issues.[3]

In addition to professional skills, a coach must be highly moral and cultured, conscientiously approach his responsibility, be honest, including love and care for children. The emergence of these features in the trainer determines the outcome of the educational process.

All-round development process - directs the trainer to form a well-rounded athlete. Sports service is inextricably linked with spiritual, mental, diligent, aesthetic and other types of education.

The study of wrestling is a healthy direction of training sessions for the one-sided growth

of sports skills and health, physical development, basic movement apparatus of athletes, cardiovascular, respiratory, including nervous by strengthening the system. Failure to follow this principle can lead to persistent, and in some cases, persistent disease in juvenile wrestlers, especially in the early stages of sports training, and is the reason why athletes with massive measures do not engage in wrestling.

Practical direction. Wrestling is of great practical importance. The practical view of this principle implies that the wrestler must be able to act unexpectedly.

The successful conduct of study-training sessions on wrestling is determined by the harmony with the main pedagogical (didactic) principles of this process.

The effectiveness of training sessions is based on the following didactic principles:

The scientific principle of teaching: The scientific principle of teaching requires the student to master the learning material and to know the scientifically-based method and procedures for organizing the teaching process. According to the scientific principle, the method of the study-training process and its organization must be scientifically based, that is, suitable for the age of the participants, including being useful for the implementation of tasks at all stages of long-term training.

The implementation of the scientific principle requires the fulfillment of a number of conditions:

- the studied actions must be accepted by students in a complete, intact state;
- the learner must understand and master the important signs and characteristics of the studied actions, the connection of the studied actions with other actions and their application during the competition;
- in the course of teaching, it is necessary to familiarize students with the easy methods of scientific research, not only the procedures for performing tasks, the results of scientific research;
- the scientific principle should introduce students only to reliable facts and knowledge confirmed in science;
- the terms accepted in science can be used in the teaching process.

Obsolete and subgroup terms cannot be used.

The principle of stability of training: The stability and intensity of training, including the alternation of load and rest between certain periods of time, form the basis of the principle of stability. The implementation of the principle of stability can be shown as an example of planning and directing the study process, creating study directions. In this case, not only the

whole of the studied material is revealed, but also the structural connections between the sections of the course. Planning the sequence of teaching is based on the rules of the following method, from specific to unknown, from easy to difficult, from simple to complex, from knowledge to experiences, from foundation to sections, from singular to general, from general to singular.[4]

The following are of great importance for the successful implementation of the principle of sustainability:

- providing participants with a comprehensive understanding of knowledge, skills and experience;
- combining all reading materials into one system, easily divided into sections;
- planning the learning of this system in accordance with the peculiarities of the participants, their studies, working conditions, alternating periods of strong employability with periods of strengthening (repetition), participation in competitions, in accordance with the conditions of the study material;
- in the actions and requirements of pedagogues, it is necessary to observe the teaching of the studied materials in a strict sequence and gradually increasing difficulty.

Demonstration principle of training: training in technical and tactical movements of wrestling begins with the formation of knowledge about movement, that is, the appearance of the studied movement with a certain concept.

The first and foremost task in practical understanding is to perceive vividly through the eyes. Providing perception through the eyes is a necessary condition for the implementation of the visual principle.[5]

The appearance of the studied method or combinations of methods is formed due to the signals coming through the organs of the eye. However, the formation of the image of the studied movement is not only through the eyes, but also other sensory organs: hearing, vestibular apparatus and e.t.c emerged through the senses.

Demonstration in teaching appears in the case where both figurative, and visual, and verbal description of the studied action at the same time.

It is necessary to take into account age, upbringing and imaginative thinking in the implementation of the demonstration principle. It is necessary to use the talent of young children to imitate and cover the task several times during the lesson. When working with older wrestlers, along with showing, the essence of the movement, its content, including the technical description, are explained. In training with wrestlers of this age, the demonstration principle is implemented through ideomotor training (imaginary repetition of the movement with special

attention to its solving phases).

The effectiveness of the use of the demonstration principle will be much higher if the performance of the action is recorded and shown through film shows.

Thus, in order to implement the demonstration principle in wrestling, the teacher must do the following:

- to explain its technical and tactical features while showing the method;
- to explain all the situations that are most convenient for performing the studied method;
- gradually explain the method according to its elements (it is desirable that this explanation makes sure about the most important elements of the method in general);
- correct selection of visual aids in general (the sequence of their use, etc.);
- to help to accept the learned technical movement as much as necessary at this stage of training.

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